

Farmer intentional pathways for net zero carbon: Exploring the lock-in effects of forestry and renewables

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Path dependency
Climate smart agriculture
Bivariate probit

ABSTRACT

Climate smart farming requires food production to sit alongside practices which sequester greenhouse gas emissions. Given the requirement to meet net zero emissions by the middle of the century, agricultural policies are now seeking to embed climate smart approaches within future support schemes. Path dependency, the influence of past choices on decision making, has been found to constrain future growth pathways. We apply this concept within a survey of 2494 farmers in Scotland to understand their intentions towards uptake of two prominent climate smart approaches, namely forestry expansion and on-farm renewable energy. We employ a bivariate probit model to estimate the single and joint dependences of these two activities within a farm decision making framework. Factors such as succession planning, the level of agricultural diversification and risk seeking perceptions were found to be positively related to influencing uptake. However, the strongest predictors for uptake were past expansion of these activities and, conversely, a limiting factor for those who did not intend to increase activities. This provides some evidence that path dependencies will limit large scale adoption to meet a net zero target. We argue for a dual approach to intervention which differentiates between past adopters and those who are reluctant to adopt. More targeted support for these two cohorts would address these high level policy ambitions.

1. Introduction

Reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by the middle of this century is now seen as a policy imperative (UN, 2015). Nationally driven efforts have resulted in the decarbonisation of a number of sectors, but others have adjusted less rapidly (Oxburgh, 2016). One case is agriculture, which has been led by the demands of a global food system and increasing population pressure to produce food in unsustainable ways (Suh et al., 2020; Dalin et al., 2019). The case of agricultural emissions reduction is now more acute as Government's unveil ambitions to meet net-zero carbon targets (e.g. Stark et al., 2019; European Commission, 2019).

An ambitious agenda towards climate smart approaches within farming has been promoted over the past decade (Lipper et al., 2014; Chandra et al., 2018). Climate smart approaches (CSA) aim to enhance resilience to climate stressors and reduce greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural production (FAO, 2017; Khatri-Chhetri et al., 2017; Mosquera-Losada et al., 2018). However, CSA has had limited success in the primary production sector (Glenk et al., 2014; Taylor, 2018;

Shilomboleni, 2020). One explanation for the slow rate of adoption is that farming is composed of multiple decision makers, with differing motivations towards land use and production (Carof et al., 2013; Barnes et al., 2013; Botero et al., 2021). Farmers are also influenced by a range of institutional forces which dictate output and production intensity (Schleyer and Plieninger, 2011; McDonagh et al., 2010). In high income countries farming is characterised by substantial government aid which ostensibly aims to support farming incomes and has a significant influence on farming decisions and performance (Aleknėvičienė et al., 2018; Minviel and Latruffe, 2017).

On-farm renewable energy generation and farm afforestation are high profile aspects of a climate smart agenda which move the farm away from food production into a source for carbon sequestration (Bhattacharyya et al., 2020; Streimikis et al., 2021; European Commission, 2020; Rudee, 2020). With increased scrutiny of greenhouse gas emissions from the agricultural sector, forestry and renewables provide a significant role off-setting greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural production (Kay et al., 2019; Aertsens et al., 2013). On farm forestry refers to the integration and the management of trees and shrubs within

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the farm. Renewable energy production accommodates a range of on-farm practices, such as anaerobic digestion of on-farm wastes or agrivoltaic systems, as well production of biomass for crops.

Several authors have examined the reasons for limited uptake of these approaches. In economic terms, both forestry expansion and renewable energy production are generally high capital projects with a long-term payoff (Xiarchos and Vick, 2011; Borchers et al., 2014). Hence, they tend to be associated with farms of a certain size, the type of system operated, the level of off-farm diversification and personal characteristics of the farmer (Xiarchos and Lazarus, 2013; Tate et al., 2012; Ge et al., 2017; Sutherland et al., 2016). Moreover, risk aversion and the opportunity cost of removing land from annual arable production, have been highlighted as significant barriers to expanding these operations (Sherrington and Moran, 2010; Djalilov et al., 2016; Nerlich et al., 2013). Where practice adoption is observed, this is around aspects that provide functionality and supporting services for other agricultural activities (Rois-Díaz et al., 2018; Barnes et al., 2021; Sutherland and Huttunen, 2018).

One explanation for reluctance may be the limited set of choices, due to past activities, available for adopting these practices, both at the farm level, but also through the demands of supply chains and policy (Mikola, 2008; Below et al., 2012). Path dependency argues that initial conditions in an economy heavily influence its subsequent development (David, 1985; Artur, 1989; Swanson, 1995; Tisdell, 2003). Although following a consistent trajectory can be a rational business decision – making efficient use of investments in infrastructure and skill development – when path dependency becomes 'locked in' this has negative results. North (1990) stressed that path dependency restricts the choice set and narrows the space in which to make decisions. Hence, it infers a historically contingent pathway which restricts options for system or technology change due to the dominance of a particular approach (Magnusson and Ottosson, 1997; Coombs and Hull, 1998). Lock-in can take numerous forms, including technological, knowledge and cultural lock-in (Sutherland et al., 2012). Individuals or institutions follow established pathways due to either the restricted costs, including the increasing returns to scale of present technologies, of changing pathways, or the social norms, institutions or knowledge around a practice (Kemp, 2000; McGuire, 2008). The effect of support policies, such as the EU Common Agricultural Policy, have also been found to embed a path dependency within farming (Kay, 2003; Wilson, 2008).

Studies focused towards farming have centred on how these lock-in effects restrict adoption of conservation-based approaches. Cowan and Gunby (1996) argued that integrated pest management, at the time, was too immature a technology to compete with current pesticide spraying and the costs of on-farm learning were too high for farmers to switch to this technology. Wilson and Tisdell (2001) also empirically examined technology 'lock-in' to explain why farmers may still use pesticides above less harmful and more environmentally sustainable approaches, finding similar barriers to change. Vanloqueren and Baret (2008) focused on adoption of wheat cultivars, finding evidence of lock-in effects due to increasing returns from pesticide application and uncertainties around Integrated Pest Management (IPM) technologies. Djanibekov et al. (2016) also found examples of legacies of central planning which constrained development of forestry in post-Soviet central Asia.

Social research has demonstrated that this pattern of 'lock in' also has social and cultural aspects: the skills and cultural identity embodied in established farming activities further reinforces path dependence (Sutherland et al., 2012). However, following a 'trigger event' – which could include farm succession or changes to subsidy access – farmers actively evaluate their trajectories, considering (and sometimes implementing) new approaches, which (if successful) become part of a new path dependency. To date very few studies have applied this approach to forestry or renewable energy. An exception is Louah et al. (2017), who argued for the case of 'cognitive' lock-in with respect to forestry adoption in temperate countries. This they defined as the result of actors

accepting the logic of underlying pathways as established and unquestionable. Cognitive lock-in was partially tested by Sereke et al. (2016), who explored whether payments for ecosystem services can change attitudes towards forestry, arguing that as long as expectations and knowledge are not appropriately addressed then financial support alone will not enable effective adoption of this practice.

The purpose of this paper is to examine the magnitude of the lock-in from past decisions, along with other structural and socio-economic factors, and how it influences future intentions towards expansion of renewable energy and forestry. We apply analysis to a large-scale survey of farmers, conducted in the Summer of 2018, across Scotland. We add to the limited number of quantified studies that have focused on path dependency in agriculture. We also examine intended adoption between renewables and forestry as both a single or joint farm decision using a bivariate probit framework. Renewable energy production and forestry are both popular forms of 'agri-environmental diversification' in Scotland – income generating diversification activities which are expected to yield environmental gains (Sutherland et al., 2016). Hence, this provides more depth to understanding how different path dependencies, (e.g. past adoption of renewables and forestry), may influence policy aims which encourage greater uptake.

The paper is structured as follows. The next section outlines the data collection approach, the choice of variables, a description of the data and the bivariate probit modelling framework. Then a discussion places these results in terms of the wider literature and implications for future research. Finally, we conclude by focusing on the policy implications and recommendations from the analysis.

2. Data and methods

Data were collected from a telephone-based survey of Scottish agricultural land managers, undertaken during the Summer of 2018. Using information from the Scottish Government's June Agricultural Census (JAC), a spatially representative sample of 11,000 businesses were selected, stratified by farm type, business size and region. The JAC reports at an agricultural holding level; therefore the data were disaggregated, where appropriate, to business level. There may be several holdings constituting a farming or crofting business – this approach therefore provides a sampling framework as representative of Scottish agriculture as far as possible. An overall response of 2494 business was gathered from the survey. The main descriptive statistics from the survey are shown below by main NUTS¹ regions. These are compared with data extracted from the Scottish June Agricultural Census.

The survey shows generally higher values at the mean for the main indicators compared to the June Agricultural Census. This reflects a more agriculturally active population compared to the census as a whole, which also accommodates diverse land ownership and many small and pluriactive businesses operating across Scotland. Accordingly, the survey respondents are those most likely to be engaged in active management of their farm business. Given the higher intensities of activity it would also seem that the survey represents cohorts of farmers most likely to respond to future support around climate related policy, compared to the wider population included in the June Agricultural Census.

The total area of farmed land varies across the regions. In the Highland and Islands rough grazing comprises a more significant component of the farm area and this shows a very large variance. The proportion of total woodland to total area is reasonably constant with an average of 5% of total area in the North East of Scotland, up to an average of 8% in the Highlands and Islands. Again these show large

¹ Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS). NUTS 2 in Scotland comprise 37 areas which are 'Combinations of council areas, local enterprise companies (LECs) and parts thereof' (see <https://www.ons.gov.uk/methodology/geography/ukgeographies/>)

variances across regions reflecting differences in management approaches to woodland within these areas. The proportion of owned land relative to land which is rented is large. The Highland and Islands show a lower proportion, reflective of the levels of tenanted farming in this region. The standard labour requirement is a measure of the workforce needed to support the agricultural output of the farm and provides an indicator of intensity of production. The more extensive farming practices in the Highlands and Islands indicate a lower full-time equivalent (FTE²), with Eastern Scotland, which has intensive arable and combinable crops, the highest. Standard outputs measure the average monetary value of the agricultural output at farm-gate prices. They provide an indication of economic size and reflect the performance of agricultural sectors regionally. With its high value livestock and crops, the North East and Eastern parts of Scotland generate the most economic value, with Highland and Islands producing the lowest.

2.1. Questionnaire development

The questionnaire formed part of a larger exercise on agricultural adaptation funded through the Scottish Government to understand the intentions of farmers to a range of phenomena. This questionnaire was developed, based on a flexible modular framework (see Barnes et al., 2016; Sutherland et al., 2016). The main sections were: i) farming background, including economic and structural factors, ii) past behaviours and iii) future intentions. These covered a range of on-farm and off-farm activities in depth.

Farmers were asked to state whether they had, in the past five years, decreased, held constant or increased a range of activities. They were then asked, as a separate block of questions, whether they intended to increase, hold constant or decrease these activities in the next five years. The main activities and intentions for this study were identified as: the amount of renewable energy production, the area of forestry and small-scale woodland. These latter two were merged to give an indication of forestry expansion.

Our main indicator of path dependency is focused on past behaviour towards these approaches. Farmers already undertaking activities are generally the most likely to plan involvement in these activities in the future (Barnes et al., 2016; Louah et al., 2017; Waş et al., 2021). Past activity should be compared with other factors that have been found to influence uptake of renewables and forestry. Previous participation in agri-environmental schemes has been found to positively affect attitudes to environmental measures (Vanslebrouck et al., 2002; Britz and Delzeit, 2013. Sutherland et al., 2016). Once land managers begin to invest in undertaking these activities, this appears to establish wider options for decision-making, where farmers are more likely to continue to maintain or increase their activities in these areas (Sutherland et al., 2016; Santiago-Freijanes et al., 2018). Tables 1 and 2 shows the explanatory variables chosen for this exercise.

Type of farming, location and specialisation of activities are characteristics that tend to influence uptake. Specialised farming systems are more likely to focus on renewables, through for example anaerobic digestion for intensive livestock farms, or solar power for specialised horticulture or arable enterprises (Hynes and Garvey, 2009). We include a categorical variable based on how much income comes from crop activities or livestock activities. Hence, higher proportions of income indicate specialisation in farming, compared to more mixed activities.

A number of studies find siting of miscanthus or woody crops and woodland on low quality land (Bocqueho and Jacquet, 2010; Duesberg et al., 2014). This satisfies the apparent desire to disaggregate agricultural production from forestry, but also the perceived economic penalties emerging from trees on farmland (Schirmer and Bull, 2014; Howley et al., 2014). Less favoured area (LFA) is land which has a

particular set of production constraints due to mostly biophysical or altitude related disadvantage. There has been much debate around the future of these areas and one aspect is the encouragement of woodland as a means to generate future payments for these traditionally low productivity areas (Hanley et al., 2007; Dax and Hellegers, 2000; O'Neill et al., 2020). Standard Labour Requirements (SLR) are a coefficient which represents the notional amount of labour required by a holding to carry out all of its agricultural activity and is used as a measure of farm size. SLR's provide a proxy for the magnitude of the farming enterprises and 1 SLR equates to 1900 working hours per year (Barnes, 2020).

The characteristics of educational level, age and gender are standard predictors of technology uptake. Studies employing these factors usually find that younger and more educated farmers tend to be more innovative (Meraner et al., 2015; Sutherland et al., 2016; Morris et al., 2017). Evidence on ownership structure is more mixed, with some studies finding landowners more willing to invest against their land capital, or tenanted farmers more prepared to extend their activities as a way to cover farming costs when compared to long term land owners (Hill, 2012). A categorical variable identifying ownership structure was used to identify this effect.

Succession and entry are also key indicators of a potential trajectory change for the farm. New entrants to farming are defined in multiple ways in policy documents, primarily based on age and recognised position as a primary farmer (Zagata and Sutherland, 2015). We defined new entrants as those who have entered the industry over the last 5 years (pre-2018). They have succeeded into management of the farm or have entered the industry for the first time. Accordingly, new entrants tend to influence a change in the business and seek alternative business opportunities (Pindado et al., 2018; Ingram and Kirwan, 2011; Jack et al., 2019). Similarly, succession planning is a key indicator as, in general, there is investment activity to make the business attractive for the successor or another investor (Sutherland et al., 2012; Barnes et al., 2016). Farmers may invest in renewable energy production in order to increase farm income to support a successor joining the farm business (Sutherland and Holstead, 2014).

Land management decisions are driven by, amongst others, market security and market forces around prices for both land and final product (Dandy, 2012). Aligned to this are attitudes to risk. Risk aversion would maintain a reliance on past norms, whereas a more risk-seeking attitude would help explain some of these wider environmental investments (Sulewski and Kloczko-Gajewska, 2014). This leads Dandy et al. (2012) to observe that pervasive perceptions of forestry as 'uneconomic' play a critical role in the creation of perceived risk in the sector. We include a binary variable to denote risk seeking behaviour, based on collapsing a 5-point Likert scale statement towards risk.

2.2. Bivariate Probit Regression

The uptake of activities can be modelled as a binary process namely no increase in uptake (0) and increase in uptake (1), and a probit modelling framework is able to model these binary outcomes. The bivariate probit model extends from the standard binary probit model and is a joint model for two binary outcomes. As such this can be specified for two outcomes (Y_1, Y_2) where the variances are assumed to be correlated. As such each pair of dependant variables has four potential outcomes (0,0), (1,0), (0,1), (1,1). The former reflects no intended increase for both outcomes, the latter an intended increase in both outcomes, with separate outcomes in-between. Hence, a bivariate probit, with two latent variables Y_1^*, Y_2^* can be estimated as:

$$Y_1^* = X_1\beta_1 + \varepsilon_1 \quad (1)$$

$$Y_2^* = X_2\beta_2 + \varepsilon_2 \quad (2)$$

Where X_1, X_2 are vectors of explanatory variables, β_1, β_2 the related coefficients to be estimated, and the error terms $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2$ which are joint

² 1 FTE is the equivalent of 1900 worked hours in a year. See: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/economic-report-scottish-agriculture-2016/pages/19/>

Table 1
Overview of farm characteristics of respondents and Scottish June Agricultural Census at business level, means and standard deviations.^a

		n	Total area		Woodland area		Amount of Owned land		Standard labour requirement		Standard output	
			Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Eastern	Survey	481	360	704	28	126	86%	40%	6.5	20	295,189	775,904
	Census	6,610	227	794	20	104	85%	34%	3.4	13.5	164,206	730,355
Highland and Islands	Survey	889	637	3,266	54	342	66%	89%	2.9	4.4	86,655	152,851
	Census	15,456	179	1,393	18	196	50%	48%	0.8	2.4	23,694	80,754
North Eastern	Survey	314	194	437	10	43	87%	36%	4.7	11.8	259,797	861,603
	Census	4,608	113	576	11	118	88%	31%	1.8	7.9	98,391	413,381
South and Western	Survey	810	287	419	18	89	86%	85%	5.2	7.9	219,085	510,450
	Census	6,377	139	352	13	139	87%	31%	2.3	5.9	102,506	222,170

^a NUTS2 figures aggregated from NUTS3 lookup. NUTS3-NUTS2 link based on: Office for National Statistics LAU2 to LAU1 to NUTS3 to NUTS2 to NUTS1 (May2016) Lookup in United Kingdom. <http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/>, Contains NationalStatistics data © Crown copyright and database right [2018].

Data source: June Agricultural Census, 2018 (business level).

Table 2
Description of explanatory variables used within the estimation.

Name	Description	Responses		
		0	1	2
Renewable energy	Activity towards renewable energy activity in the past 5 years (0. Stay the same, 1. Increased).	79%	21%	
Forestry	Activity towards forestry activity in the past 5 years (0. Stay the same, 1. Increased).	89%	11%	
Agri-environmental scheme	Activity towards agri-environmental scheme participation in the past 5 years (0. Stay the same, 1. Increased).	80%	20%	
Livestock specialisation	Specialised livestock farming types in cattle, dairy, poultry and pigs (0. Mixed, 1. Specialist).	87%	13%	
Crop specialisation	Specialised cropping farming types, in cereals, horticulture or permanent crops (0. Mixed, 1. Specialist).	93%	7%	
LFA	Whether the farm is located in a Less Favoured Area (0. No, 1. Yes).	29%	71%	
Successor	Whether a succession plan is in place (0. No, 1. Yes).	54%	46%	
New Entrant	Whether the respondent has entered farming in the last 5 years (0. No, 1. Yes).	92%	8%	
Risk seeker	Response to the statement "I'm willing to take substantial investment risks to earn substantial returns" (0. Disagree, 1. Agree or Strongly Agree).	49%	51%	
Income from Agriculture	Percentage share of total income from agricultural activities (0. <25%, 1: 25–75%, 2: >75%).	23%	27%	50%
Ownership	Farm ownership structure (0. Owner-Occupied, 1. Tenanted, 2. Mixed).	64%	17%	19%
Age	Farmer age category (0. <45, 1. 45–64, 2. 65+).	14%	54%	33%
Education	Highest level of education of the main decision maker, (0. School only, 1. College Award, 2. University Degree or higher)	35%	36%	28%
SLR	Standard labour requirement of the farm in full-time equivalents (1 Full time equivalent equates to 1900 h), presented at the mean	4.54		

normal with means = 0 and variance = 1 with a correlation parameter (ρ) for the two marginal distributions. The joint probability of the four outcomes is modelled as:

$$Y_1 = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } Y_1^* > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } Y_1^* \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$Y_2 = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } Y_2^* > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } Y_2^* \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The coefficients and correlation parameters are estimated using maximum likelihood estimation. We apply the biprobit function within Stata 16.0 (Stata Corp, 2019), taking the same explanatory variables for both sets of intentions.

3. Results

Table 3 shows the distribution of responses for the four choices available. Around 67% of farmers expressed no intentions to expand in the next five years. In terms of separate activities, 13% of respondents were intending to increase renewables, whereas 12% were intending increase forestry. Overall, only 8% of the sample were intending to increase both activities.

Table 4 shows the estimated coefficients from the bivariate probit, with standard errors clustered to control for individual variance. This shows the parameter estimates of two probit models and, critically, shows the correlation parameter (ρ) value as significantly different from 0. This means that a bivariate structure is preferred to two separate probit regressions as there is some structural linkage between the two dependant variables (Greene, 2000). Other test statistics are strong: the Wald chi² indicates the log likelihood of the fitted model, compared to an intercept only model, is significant.

The coefficients within the table show the direction of the effects and their significance on uptake of renewables and forestry. These indicate the three past activity variables have a positive effect on the decision to increase activity further and are mostly significant. In other words, this indicates that expanding activity in the past will positively predict intentions to increase activity in the future, providing an indication of path dependency. In addition, other factors such as farm specialisation, as well as institutional and farm family life cycles have a positive influence on the intention to increase activity.

The raw parameter estimates give some indication of the influence of

Table 3
Intentions to increase activity in the next five years.

	Forestry					
	Stay the Same		Increase		(N)	
	(%)	n	(%)	n		
Renewables	Stay the Same	(67%)	1,679	(12%)	295	1,974
	Increase	(13%)	319	(8%)	201	520
			1,998		496	2,494

Table 4
Bivariate probit regression coefficient estimates and standard errors for renewables and forestry, maximum-likelihood two-equation probit model.

	Renewables		Forestry	
	Coef.	Std. Err.	Coef.	Std. Err.
<i>Increased level of activity past 5 years</i>				
Renewables	0.356 ***	0.071	0.158 *	0.076
Forestry	0.113 –	0.091	0.99 ***	0.089
Agri-environmental scheme	0.349 ***	0.072	0.354 ***	0.074
Livestock specialisation	0.281 **	0.095	0.042 –	0.1
Crop specialisation	0.316 *	0.123	-0.158 –	0.144
LFA	-0.156 *	0.076	-0.314 ***	0.08
Successor	0.236 ***	0.064	0.02 –	0.065
New entrant	0.441 ***	0.111	0.051 –	0.118
Risk seeker	0.326 ***	0.061	0.181 **	0.064
<i>Income from Agriculture (reference < 25%)</i>				
25–75%	0.032 –	0.085	-0.026 –	0.086
75%+	-0.155 *	0.078	-0.163 *	0.078
<i>Ownership (reference: owner-occupied)</i>				
Tenanted	0.037 –	0.079	0.036 –	0.081
Mixed	-0.229 **	0.084	-0.188 *	0.084
<i>Age (reference < 45)</i>				
45–64	-0.069 –	0.091	-0.08 –	0.093
65+	-0.253 *	0.104	-0.082 –	0.104
<i>Education (reference: school only)</i>				
College	0.162 *	0.073	0.181 *	0.076
University	0.289 ***	0.079	0.254 **	0.08
SLR	0.000 –	0.002	0.000 –	0.002
ρ	0.369***			
Wald test of ρ	70.922***			
Wald χ^2	449.71***			
Log likelihood	-2222.54			

^ *0.05; **0.01; ***0.001

the explanatory variables on the outcomes whereas Table 5 shows the marginal predicted probabilities on each of the four outcomes. This is estimated by taking each outcome separately at the mean. The marginal effects show the change in the probability of each outcome variable when the predictor variable changes by one unit. Hence, the estimates give an indication of both the size and direction of the effect from a 1% increase in a continuous explanatory variable or a discrete change from

Table 5
Bivariate marginal predicted probabilities for each outcome.

	Stay the Same		Increase Forestry		Increase Renewables		Increase Forestry & Renewables	
	m.e	s.e	m.e	s.e	m.e	s.e	m.e	s.e
<i>Increased level of activity past 5 years</i>								
Renewables	-0.101 ***	0.023	0.005 –	0.014	0.06 ***	0.014	0.036 ***	0.008
Forestry	-0.209 ***	0.026	0.178 ***	0.018	-0.048 *	0.019	0.079 ***	0.010
Agri-environmental scheme	-0.137 ***	0.022	0.043 **	0.014	0.045 **	0.014	0.049 ***	0.008
Livestock specialisation	-0.064 *	0.029	-0.012 –	0.019	0.053 **	0.019	0.022 *	0.010
Crop specialisation	-0.034 –	0.041	-0.052 –	0.026	0.075 **	0.025	0.010 –	0.015
LFA	0.090 ***	0.023	-0.048 **	0.015	-0.009 –	0.015	-0.033 ***	0.009
Successor	-0.051 **	0.019	-0.013 –	0.012	0.046 ***	0.013	0.018 *	0.007
New entrant	-0.098 **	0.034	-0.021 –	0.022	0.085 ***	0.022	0.034 **	0.012
Risk seeker	-0.102 ***	0.019	0.010 –	0.012	0.054 ***	0.013	0.038 ***	0.008
<i>Income from Agriculture (reference < 25%)</i>								
25–75%	-0.002 –	0.027	-0.008 –	0.017	0.009 –	0.018	0.000 –	0.011
75%+	0.062 **	0.024	-0.020 –	0.015	-0.019 –	0.016	-0.022 *	0.009
<i>Ownership (reference: owner-occupied)</i>								
Tenanted	-0.015 –	0.024	0.004 –	0.016	0.005 –	0.017	0.006 –	0.009
Mixed	0.077 **	0.023	-0.020 –	0.015	-0.032 *	0.015	-0.026 ***	0.007
<i>Age (reference < 45)</i>								
45–64	0.030 –	0.029	-0.010 –	0.018	-0.008 –	0.020	-0.012 –	0.011
65+	0.066 *	0.032	0.002 –	0.020	-0.044 *	0.022	-0.024 *	0.012
<i>Education (reference: school only)</i>								
College	-0.064 **	0.021	0.023 –	0.014	0.019 –	0.014	0.022 **	0.007
University	-0.106 ***	0.024	0.027 –	0.015	0.040 *	0.016	0.038 ***	0.009
SLR	0.000 –	0.001	0.000 –	0.000	0.000 –	0.000	0.000 –	0.000

marginal estimates, |standard error *0.05; **0.01; ***0.001

0 to 1 for a categorical variable (Christofides et al., 1997). These outcomes are categorised as no intentions to increase activity, an intention to increase forestry only, an intention to increase renewables only and intentions to increase both forestry and renewables.

Compared to those who did not expand their forestry, if the land manager increased their activity in the past five years there is an 18% probability of future expansion. For renewables this effect is lower but still has a positive influence. Similarly, for those intending to increase both renewables and forestry, past activities positively influence the outcome. Conversely, the probability of no intention to expand is reduced by 10% if the land manager has increased renewables in the last five years. For forestry, this effect is almost double. Another influence is past participation in agri-environmental schemes, which also has a positive influence on the intention to expand further. Accordingly, there is an influence of past behaviour having a significant effect on dictating future outcomes. This provides some indication of a path dependency operating within the farming community and seems to reveal a particularly intractable barrier to those not wishing to expand in the future.

Farm specialisation has been found to be positive towards renewables adoption. This reflects the need for large quantities of inputs to enable cost-effective adoption, for example waste from dairy farming to feed an anaerobic digester (O'Connor et al., 2020). We find specialisation has a positive influence on those intending to expand renewables within the livestock sector. For arable farms, specialisation has a negative effect on forestry expansion. This reflects competition between using productive land for agricultural activity and concern around 'locking up' land under forestry (Nerlich et al., 2013; Djililov et al., 2016). Compared to land which is owner operated, tenanted land has proven to be a barrier for increasing activities and reflects issues around arrangements for land use and long-term planning (Ge et al., 2017; Tsonkova et al., 2018). Moreover, this may indicate that those farmers using more rented land to expand their businesses are doing so for purely agricultural purposes with no intention of alternative uses.

Off-farm diversification activity was proxied by the proportion of total income from agricultural, compared to non-agricultural, sources. Those with at least 75% of their total income from farming are less likely to expand forestry or renewables. Previous studies have found a positive link between off-farm diversification and uptake of environmental activities (O'Connell and Osmond, 2018; Khanal et al., 2019).

Accordingly, this would seem consistent with our finding that those with low levels of off-farm diversification are less likely to engage in forestry or renewable activities.

Age is negatively related to expanding forestry and renewable activities (Tranter et al., 2011; Tate et al., 2012), with younger farmers more likely to invest in these activities. Relative to farmers under 45, farmers over 65 have a 7% probability of not choosing to expand their activities. Education levels also positively influence the choice for increasing renewables and forestry activity (Sollen-Norrlin et al., 2020). Relative to farmers with school-only education, university graduates have a 4% probability of increasing activities, and college graduates a 2% probability.

Succession planning has a positive influence on the intention to increase both forestry and renewables. This reflects the transitional change enabled from a handover in decision making (Barnes et al., 2016; Sutherland et al., 2016). Compared to traditional farmers, new entrants have a 9% probability of expanding their renewables, and also a 3% probability of expanding both activities. Consequently new entrants would be expected to be more open to non-food production related activities when compared with traditional farmers (Pindado et al., 2018; Jack et al., 2019). Moreover, the risk seeking variable found a positive relationship for those intending to expand renewables. This indicates that, compared to those who expressed a risk aversion, there is a 5% greater probability of increasing renewable energy production, and a 4% greater probability of increasing both renewable energy and forestry. This is reflective of the approach to gaining a return from the large capital spend needed to invest in expanding these activities (Spiegel et al., 2018; Haldar and Damodaran, 2021).

4. Discussion

Within high income countries there is a growing emphasis on policy outcomes which move away from food production and begin to challenge the traditional productivist trajectories of farming. These now encompass more ambitious adoption of climate smart approaches to meet nationally determined goals for greenhouse gas emissions. However, we find a strong influence of past activity on intended activities and this path dependency is a major barrier to achieving policy objectives for change.

Accordingly, to facilitate a substantial transition towards forestry and renewable energy production requires an intervention agenda which supports businesses to change their current trajectories. A range of factors have been found to support this shift and we find discrete sets of influences dictating the choice to expand further into renewables or forestry. Past engagement in agri-environmental programmes are positively related to intentions to expand both forestry and renewables, and have been found to provide support for developing the depth and the range of environmental activities on farm (Vanslebrouck et al., 2002; Britz, and Delzeit, 2013; Sutherland et al., 2016; Gatto et al., 2019). Widening these support programmes, through redistribution from income-support to environmental payments, is becoming the aim of most agricultural support regimes. However, whilst partly supported by increasing agri-environmental scheme activity the circumstances of the farm and farm household are also pertinent.

Formal education and encouraging new entrants is positively related to intentions to expand non-agricultural activities. Education reflects an aspect of engagement with newer perspectives that could challenge any technology lock-ins within farming (Artur, 1989; Wilson and Tidsell, 2001). Cohorts of new entrants tend to be more willing to expand or engage in other activities such as renewables and forestry, partially as a means to generate income and capture agri-environment subsidies (Hird, 2017; Gold et al., 2009; Lewis and Wiser, 2007). Hence, reluctance to expand may be evidence of a 'cognitive', or behavioural, lock-in effect preventing adoption of these activities (Barnes et al., 2004; Sutherland et al., 2012; Louah et al., 2017). The farmer may not consider these forestry or renewables as options because they require a highly

knowledge intensive process. This perspective has been found to be a barrier to adoption of agri-environmental schemes and environmental activities generally (McGuire et al., 2013; Sulemana and James, 2014; Gatto et al., 2019). Moreover, it may reveal a status quo bias, where individuals naturally reject change and prefer to continue current practices (Samuelson and Zeckhauser, 1988; Hermann et al., 2016; Barreiro-Hurle et al., 2018). These studies argue that current policy has been unwilling to fully address this resistance and this bias has also been identified in European agricultural policy, which tends to limit change, partially through the presence of lobbying (Telesetsky et al., 2017; Pokrivcak and Swinnen, 2002).

Whilst a simple metric is used here for measuring risk tolerance, a common finding in the literature is that adoption is characterised by less risk aversion (Caldas et al., 2014; Paul et al., 2017). Risk aversion may reflect, perhaps indirectly, the perceived uncertainty towards renewables and forestry (Cowan and Gunby, 1996; Xiarchos and Vick, 2011; Borchers et al., 2014) which compounds concern over the financial risk around investment (Trujillo-Berrera et al., 2016; Dessart et al., 2019), and leads to unwillingness to change pathways (Blyth, 2002). The opportunity costs of switching to non-traditional activities is also a barrier to these practices. This calls for more knowledge sharing and practice adoption observed through peer-to-peer learning mechanisms which enable and support farmers to invest in these practices (Skaalsveen et al., 2020; Botero et al., 2021).

Specialised enterprises are most likely to invest in renewables as a means to manage the significant cost burden of these activities (Pascaris et al., 2020; Harrison and Ndegwa, 2020). Mbzibain et al. (2013) found the high investment cost to be the main economic barrier to adoption and was less prevalent in large scale specialised enterprises. Reluctance to expand may also reflect the perspective of a farm household operating within a fragile financial system (Shadbolt et al., 2013; Barnes et al., 2020) but also argues for adaptation or transformations of that system to embed resilience, such as those offered with climate smart approaches (Walker et al., 2009; Geels, 2014; Darnhofer, 2014).

The role of succession planning proved to be a positive predictor behind expansion of these activities. Succession planning is generally found to have a positive effect on performance (Barnes et al., 2016; Bertoni et al., 2016) but also on the adoption of agri-environmental intentions (Pedroli and Langeveld, 2011; Sutherland et al., 2016; Riley, 2006). Land management structures, in particular the role of tenure, is a prevalent barrier to investment (Graves et al., 2009; Borremans et al., 2018). Tenancy agreements tend to restrict longer term activity such as expanding the current woodland on farm, but also non-agricultural production activities, such as investments in renewables.

5. Conclusions

Path dependency emerged as an institutional construct which can equally be applied at a micro-economic scale, as it refers to the dynamic pattern that evolves from its own past (David, 2007). The current trajectory of a farm is determined by past perturbations, particular outlooks, habits and restrictive economic structures (Wilson, 2007), and the buffering effect of support regimes have tended to limit the opportunistic response to a turbulent environment (Levi, 1997; Sutherland et al., 2012; Meuwissen et al., 2019). The results presented here support the contention that outcomes are strongly associated with past trajectories and, therefore, provide evidence of a path dependency which will challenge recent policy ambitions for the farming sector. This is becoming more acute under commitments to address greenhouse gas emissions, as well as ambitions around supporting frameworks for biodiversity. The English agricultural agency Defra has set out a 7 year transition to a public goods model in which income support will be removed and payment predicated on adoption of environmental activities (Defra, 2021). The EU's Farm to Fork Strategy, while less radical, aims to shift perspectives towards new rationales of climate and

biodiversity which will dictate entitlements for funding agriculture (Klaar et al., 2020; Montanarella and Panagos, 2021).

We find different intentions towards activities across the Scottish farming population and this may indicate how particular schemes to promote public goods could be targeted. In some ways the responses recorded here infer a farming style, which reflects the approach to land use and the cultural values placed on symbols around 'productivist' agriculture (Burton, 2004; Burton et al., 2008). This is especially prevalent for forestry, where numerous authors have found a stated preference for agricultural production and this is a barrier to expansion of trees on farm (Valdivia et al., 2012; Garcia de Jalón et al., 2018). Accordingly, increasing forestry and renewables should involve a two-pronged approach with payments targeted to the subset of farmers more open to planting, i.e. those already involved in forestry and renewables, and separate, more nuanced promotion of activities aimed at land managers previously uninvolved in forestry or renewables (Hopkins et al., 2017). Moreover, this would capitalise on cohorts with different degrees of experiential learning (Okumah et al., 2021). Additionally, promoting initiatives around succession would increase the uptake of these activities, as identification of a successor is considered a disruptive event and offers opportunities for re-orientation of the farm (Cavicchioli et al., 2018; Bertolozzi-Caredio et al., 2020). A more restrictive barrier is land tenure. If the ambition of support is to increase the amount of non-farm production activities then engagement must encourage dialogue and contractual change between tenants and landlords to allow longer-term schemes to operate on farm.

The concept of a behavioural or cognitive lock-in also seems important here, as the encouragement of education and new entrants has a positive impact on expansion of climate smart activities. Supporting knowledge acquisition and peer-to-peer learning may overcome some of the prejudices that are restricting farmer engagement in these practices. Arguably, forestry and renewables will become more ubiquitous as they benefit from stronger financial support. This would lead to an increase in opportunities to access and engage in climate smart knowledge sharing and experiences.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge Dave Miller (James Hutton Institute) for his assistance in interpretation of June Agricultural Census data, and Douglas Wardell-Johnson (James Hutton Institute) for his work in processing Agricultural Census data. This research was funded by the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme on Economic Resilience and Adaptation (WP 2.4.1/2.4.2). AB is also grateful for funding from the LIFT (Low Income Farming and Territories) European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 770747.

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